

IMPROVING THE CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS DURING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PEDAGOGICAL CLASSES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13764147>

Abstract. This article describes the essence of the concepts of "competence" and "professional competence", the qualities of professional competence, and the development of the professional competence of a pedagogue.

Key words: competence, professional competence, qualities of professional competence, pedagogical professional competence, "Individual development program", self-development, stages of work on oneself.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ХОДЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА В ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КЛАССАХ

Аннотация. В статье раскрывается сущность понятий «компетенция» и «профессиональная компетентность», качества профессиональной компетентности, развитие профессиональной компетентности педагога.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, профессиональная компетентность, качества профессиональной компетентности, педагогическая профессиональная компетентность, «Индивидуальная программа развития», саморазвитие, этапы работы над собой.

The essence of the concepts of "competence" and "professional competence". In the conditions of market relations, resistance to strong competition, which takes priority in the labor market, requires every specialist to have professional competence and to improve it consistently.

"Competence" (incl. "competency" - "ability") - the effective use of theoretical knowledge in activities, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional qualifications, skill and talent

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, has a plan of action in consistently developing and complex processes."

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the mastering of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

Development of professional competence of the teacher. Self-work and self-development are important in acquiring professional (including pedagogical) competence.

The tasks of self-development are determined through self-analysis and self-evaluation.

Work on oneself is the organization of purposeful, consistent, systematic actions by a person or specialist in order to develop oneself socially and professionally, to reach perfection.

The following practical actions of the pedagogue represent his work on himself as a specialist:

- improving professional BKM;
- critical and creative participation in activities;
- achieving professional and creative cooperation;
- development of work ability;
- eliminating negative habits;
- acquisition of positive qualities.

The individual development program of a pedagogue is a personal-practical program developed by a pedagogue as a specialist based on the needs of formation and development of professional-pedagogical qualities, knowledge, skills, qualifications, professional competence.

Components of pedagogical skill and their essence. The concept of "pedagogical skill" began to be taught as an independent subject in HEIs based on scientific and pedagogical aspects in the 80s and 90s of the last century. and when the subject of "technology" began to be taught, the basics of the subject of "Pedagogical skills" were absorbed into its content. In the system of retraining pedagogic personnel and improving their qualifications, it is appropriate to familiarize students with the basics of pedagogical skills on the basis of the module "Basics of pedagogical competence and creativity". After all, introducing the structural elements of pedagogical skill by the listeners, assimilation of information about the pedagogical technique, speech culture, pedagogical deontology, communicative ability, pedagogical conflict, as well as the image of a modern pedagogue and the acquisition of necessary skills based on this knowledge, improving the quality of the pedagogical process organized in HEIs, guarantees the effectiveness.

In the process of familiarizing students with pedagogical skill and its structural elements under the module "Pedagogical competence and creativity", the following tasks are solved: arming students with theoretical knowledge of the components of pedagogical skill; to develop in them the skills and abilities of rational organization of pedagogical activity, effective implementation of the pedagogical process; ensure that listeners have pedagogical and speech techniques; inculcate in them the qualities of pedagogical deontology and pedagogical culture, develop pedagogical skills; pedagogical communication by listeners, педагогик назорат (такт) ва педагогик таъсир кўрсатиш малакаларини етарли даражада ўзлаштирилишини таъминлаш; уларда педагогик маданият сифатларини шакллантириш. Олий таълим муассасалари педагогларининг касбий маҳоратлари ҳақида сўз юритишдан аввал "маҳорат" ва "педагогик маҳорат" тушунчаларининг моҳияти билан танишиб олиш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

In different regions of the world, creative ideas became the basis for the development of human culture, the development of natural sciences, philosophy, art and humanities. Creative thinking is different from just random thinking. Creative thinking is a real competence based on knowledge and experience, which creates conditions for people to achieve expected results in tense and complex situations. The mission of education is to provide students with the necessary competencies to succeed in the future. Because of this, they help adapt to a world that is changing rapidly in the process of globalization, literacy and digitization are promoted, and flexible workers with modern requirements.

As a result of the acquisition of creative thinking by young students, they develop the ability to use new technologies to solve current problems, to work in sectors that have not yet been created, as well as to perform tasks that cannot be done by machines and to solve global problems.

The importance of schools in the life of the society is that it is to make students feel that they are a part of the society, to make their contribution to the development of the society and to fulfill their duties in front of it. International studies, by increasing students' creative thinking, ensure that they approach experiences, events and situations in a new way, and help them gain knowledge. In order to accelerate the student's thinking, curiosity and motivation, it is necessary to develop new styles of technology and forms of learning that reveal new aspects of his creativity.

These developmental learning styles help slow learners to express themselves and increase their interests. Creative thinking can be purposeful and practical, like other skills. In the eyes of some teachers, increasing the student's creative thinking seems to involve engaging in other activities outside the curriculum. In fact, the ability of students to think creatively in all subjects is taken into account. Another advantage of creative thinking is that the student acquires basic knowledge not by memorization, but by supporting the ability to search and discover. Creative thinking is a way of thinking that leads to the creation of valuable and original ideas. All people can engage in creative thinking and "everyday" creativity (finding non-standard solutions to everyday problems). Creative thinking can be used not only in the creation of creative works or imaginative situations related to art, but also in tasks that are functional in other areas, such as solving problems or social issues.

The ideas used in the PISA international program of the competence model of creative thinking can be as follows: in the form of answers to questions about written, visual, social problems and scientific phenomena. In the test sections, open-type tasks and contexts are provided that determine the ability of students to express new opinions. The result of the test sections can reveal all aspects of creative thinking at the international level. Even in such a situation, test departments cannot control all aspects of the competency model. Evaluating students' ideas requires appropriate cognitive skills, professional and creative experiences. How many ideas a person can express depends on him. shows the ability to think creatively. This situation shows that he has a deep thought. Creative thinking sets a goal in front of him and ends with the desired result.

Expected creative thinking skills are not characterized by the creation of unusual innovations, but by the fact that they are creative activities that give the desired result. Assessing the students' thinking processes helps to find effective and productive ideas. New ideas are found in these processes. or existing ideas are reshaped. Processes of repetition and evaluation can be the basis of creative thinking. The skill formed due to the ability to identify the flaws and conveniences in the ideas given by other people from the outside serves as the basis for working as a team.

REFERENCES

1. Каршиева, Д. К. О'quvchilarda kreativ fikrlashni rivojlantirishda xalqaro tadqiqotlarning o'rni / Д. К. Каршиева, О. Н. Усмонова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2023. — № 2 (449). — С. 500-505. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/449/98832/> (дата обращения: 13.09.2024).

2. Innovatsion taʼlim texnologiyalari va pedagogik kompetentlik moduli boyicha oʻquv-uslubiy majmua – Toshkent. 2016
3. Jorayev P.X., Raximov B.X., Xomatov SH.F. Yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar. Muammoli taʼlim aasoslangan oʻquv-metodik qolanma. –T.: Fan, 2005, 66 b.
4. Adizov B. Boshlangʻich taʼlimni ijodiy tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari: Ped. fan. dok. ... dis. –Toshkent, 2003. – 276 b. 8. Aliyev A. Oʻquvchilarning ijodkorlik qobiliyati. – Toshkent: Oʻqituvchi,1991.40bet